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Derleme Makalesi/ Review Article

Contributions Made By Researchers To The Turkish Chrysomelidae Fauna, Which Has Been Updated With The Addition of Many Species Groups Taxa Since 2014

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Abstract

This article includes new species, new subspecies, new records and new records for provinces added to the fauna of Turkey Chrysomelidae since 2014. This study, It has been prepared by considering the publications of researchers who have contributed to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna since 2014. Since 2014, Turkish and foreign researchers have added a total of 15 new species (*Labidostomis (Labidostomis) leonardii* sp. nov., *Bruchidius planicornis* sp. nov., *Luperus doeberli* n. sp., *Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cilicius* n. sp., *Rhodopaea heinzi* sp.n. *Scelolyperus perreus* Bezděk sp. nov., *Chrysolina (Lopatinica) kabalaki* sp. n., *Cheilotoma cankiriensis* spec. nov., *Labidostomis atkaracalarica* sp. nov., *Hydrothassa (Agrostithassa) anatolica* sp. nov., *Argopus circumaeadeagus* sp. nov., *Cassida alidagiense* sp. nov.; *Aphthona harputensis* sp. nov.; *Phyllotreta bilgeae* sp. nov.; *Phyllotreta aygulae* sp. nov.) 18 new registrations and 2 new record subspecies (*Cryptocephalus rugicollis otomana* sub sp. n., *Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) sanguineocincta pinarbasiense* subsp. nov.) to the Chrysomelidae fauna in Turkey. As a result, with the contributions of Turkish and foreign researchers, 4 new species belonging to the Alticinae subfamily; 1 new species belonging to Bruchinae subfamily; 1 new species belonging to Cassidinae subfamily; 3 new species and 1 subspecies belonging to subfamily Chrysomelinae; 3 new species belonging to the subfamily Clytrinae; 2 new species belonging to Galerucinae subfamily and 1 new species belonging to Eumolpinae subfamily have been added to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna. The number of subfamily species increased with new species and new subspecies on 7 subfamilies. Which researcher contributed to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey which study is seen in the tables given in our study.

Keywords: Chrysomelidae, new species, new records, Turkish Fauna and Turkey

INTRODUCTION

The family Chrysomelidae is one of the most important and species-rich families of the order Coleoptera (Kismalı, 1973; Lopatin, 1977). The family Chrysomelidae is represented all over the world by more than 38000 species and 2500 genera belonging to 19 subfamilies (Seeno & Wilcox, 1982). The members of the Chrysomelidae family, which has a worldwide distribution outside the Arctic region, are represented by 3500 species in 560 genera in the Palearctic region and 930 species in 91 genera in Turkey. (Riley et al., 2002; Aslan et al., 2014; Aslan & Alkan, 2015; Bal et al., 2016b; Ekiz et al., 2013; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Özdikmen et al., 2014; Özdikmen & Bal, 2016). Turkey is one of the countries with the richest biodiversity in Europe and the Middle East and ranks ninth in terms of biodiversity in the European continent. (Özhatay et al., 2003). We reach the lists of species related to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna collectively from the studies of Ekiz et al. in 2013 and Özdikmen et al. in 2014 (Ekiz et al., 2013; Özdikmen et al., 2014; Özdikmen H., 2014a; Özdikmen H., 2014b; Özdikmen et al., 2014; Özdikmen & Kaya, 2014; Özdikmen & Mercan, 2014; Özdikmen & Cihan, 2014; Özdikmen & Özbek, 2014; Özdikmen & Kavak, 2014; Özdikmen & Topçu, 2014). Since that date, various fauna-related studies have been carried out at the subfamily level or by giving a field of study, and no collective checklist has been given related to them. In this study, new species, new subspecies, new records for Turkey and new records for provinces are included in the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey after 2014. Over the years, we can easily see that the number of studies on the Chrysomelidae family has increased in our country. Turkish researchers who have contributed to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna since 2014; Ali GÖK, Ali NAFİZ EKİZ, Ayçin YILMAZ, Baran ASLAN, Cemil YETKİN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, Ebru GÜL ASLAN, Ebru ÜNAL, Ergin TURANTEPE, Esat PEHLİVAN, Fatma

BAYRAM, Gamze KAYA, Halil BOLU, Hüseyin ÖZBEK, Hüseyin ŞENDIKMEN, Kadir BOSTAN, Kübra ALKAN, Medine BAŞAR, Meltem KAVAK, Naciye CİHAN, Naciye NUR TOPÇU, Neslihan BAL, Nihal MERCAN, Özgür Durmuş Kaya, Serdar TEZCAN, Tülin KILIÇ and Yusuf KARSAVURAN. Foreign researchers who have contributed to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna since 2014; Alex DELOBEL, Elisabeth GEISER, Franck DUHALDEBORDE, Gloria BASTAZO, HORST KIPPENBERG, Jan BEZDEK, Jose MIQUEL VELA, Klaus-Wemer ANTON, Lev. NIKANDROVICH. MEDVEDEV, Matthias SCHOLLER and Renato REGALÍN.

MATERIAL and METHOD

This study, It has been prepared by considering the publications of researchers who have contributed to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna since 2014. We reach the lists of species related to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna collectively from the studies of Ekiz et al. in 2013 and Özdikmen et al. in 2014 (Ekiz et al., 2013; Özdikmen et al., 2014; Özdikmen H., 2014a; Özdikmen H., 2014b; Özdikmen et al., 2014; Özdikmen & Kaya, 2014; Özdikmen & Mercan, 2014; Özdikmen & Cihan, 2014; Özdikmen & Özbek, 2014; Özdikmen & Kavak, 2014; Özdikmen & Topçu, 2014). The studies up to the present have been researched and examined, and the new species added to the fauna, new subspecies, new records, new records for the provinces, and the necessary information about the researcher group and the article are presented in tables.

RESULTS

The studies contributing to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey are given below in order of date.

1. Turkish Researchers Who Have Contributed To The Chrysomelidae Fauna Of Turkey Since 2014

1.1. Baran ASLAN, Fatma BAYRAM and Ebru GÜL ASLAN, 2014

In 2015, Aslan B., Bayram and Aslan, E. G. provided new record for Aydın

province with their study. This is included in table 1 below.

Table1. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

First Record of the Flea Beetle <i>Psylliodes wrasei</i> Leonardi and Arnold (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini) in Turkey: A Promising Biological Control Agent for Hoary Cress, <i>Lepidium draba</i> L. (Brassicaceae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Psylliodes wrasei</i> Leonardi and Arnold, 1995	It has been recorded for the first time from southwest Turkey (Aydın province)

1.2. Fatma BAYRAM and Ebru GÜL ASLAN, 2015

their study. This is included in table 2 below.

In 2015, Bayram and Aslan provided new record for Aydın province and Turkey with

Table 2.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Comparison of Alticini (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae) species diversity in different habitats selected from Bafa Lake Natural Park (Aydın) basin with a new record for Turkish fauna		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Longitarsus aeruginosus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	<u>It has been recorded for the first time from Turkey (Aydın province)</u>

1.3. Ebru GÜL ASLAN and Kübra ALKAN, 2015

their study. These are included in table 3 below.

In 2015, Aslan and Alkan provided new record for İsparta province and Turkey with

Table 3.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

The Alticini (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae) fauna of Davraz Mountain (İsparta): comments on host plant and altitude preferences with two new records for Turkish fauna		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Longitarsus brunneus</i> (Duftschmidt, 1825)	<u>It has recorded for the first time in Turkey (İsparta province)</u>
	<i>Psylliodes laticollis</i> Kutschera, 1864	<u>It has recorded for the first time in Turkey (İsparta province)</u>

1.4. Baran ASLAN, Ayçin YILMAZ, Fatma BAYRAM and Ebru GÜL ASLAN, 2015

In 2015, Aslan B., Yılmaz, Bayram and Aslan, E. G. provided new record for Burdur province with their study. These are included in table 4 below.

Table 4.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Contributions To The Insect Fauna Of Burdur Province (Turkey) In Terms Of Hydrophilidae, Helophoridae And Chrysomelidae(Coleoptera) With Chorotype Analyses		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta erysimi</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta fornuseki</i> Cizek, 2003	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta maculicornis</i> Pic, 1906	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta variipennis</i> (Boieldieu, 1859)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Phyllotreta vittula</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Aphthona pygmaea</i> (Kutschera, 1861)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Longitarsus aeneicollis</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Longitarsus karlheinzii</i> Warchalowski, 1972	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Longitarsus longipennis</i> Kutschera, 1863	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Longitarsus reichei</i> (Allard, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Longitarsus succineus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Altica ancyrensis</i> (Weise, 1897)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema arenaceae</i> (Allard, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema breviscula</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema concinna</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema conducta</i> (Motschulsky, 1838)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema coyei</i> (Allard, 1863)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Psylliodes circumdata</i> (Redtenbacher, 1842)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Psylliodes cuprea</i> (Koch, 1803)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Psylliodes isatidis</i> Heikertinger, 1912	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Psylliodes ozisiki</i> Leonardi et Arnold, 1995	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Psylliodes tricolor</i> Weise, 1888	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Psylliodes vindobonensis</i> Heikertinger, 1914	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Crepidodera aurata</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Podagrica malvae</i> (Illiger, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.

1.5. İsmail ŞEN, 2015

In 2015, Şen provided new species for Van province with his study. This is included in table 5 below.

Table 5.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A new species of the genus <i>Chrysolina</i> Motschulsky, 1860 from Turkey (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina (Lopatinica) kabalaki</i> sp. n.	New species (Van Province)

1.6. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and CEMİL YETKİN, 2015

In 2015, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Yetkin provided new record for Şanlıurfa province with their study. This is included in table 6 below.

Table 6.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

New Records of Subgenus <i>Paradiachalcoidea</i> Daccordi, 1978 and <i>Chrysolina Dohrnii</i> (Fairmaire, 1865) For Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae: Chrysolina)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina (Paradiachalcoidea) dohrynii dohrynii</i>	<u>It has been recorded for the first time from Turkey (Sanliurfa province)</u>

1.7. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN and Neslihan BAL, 2016

In 2016, Özdikmen and Bal provided new species and new record for Çankırı province

with their study. These are included in table 7 below.

Table 7.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species Of <i>Cheilotoma</i> Chevrolat From Turkey With An Updated List (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Clytrinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Cheilotoma cankiriensis</i> spec. nov.	New species (Çankırı Province)
	<i>Cheilotoma beldei</i> Kasap, 1984	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.

1.8. Neslihan BAL, Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN and Suat KIYAK, 2016

In 2016, Bal, Özdikmen and Kıyak provided new record for Çankırı province

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 8 below.

Table 8.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Record To The Genus <i>Pachnephorus</i> Chevrolat Of Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Eumolpinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Eumolpinae</i> Hope, 1840	<i>Pachnephorus corinthius</i> Fairmaire, 1862	<u>It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Çankırı province)</u>
	<i>Pachnephorus villosus</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.

1.9. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Neslihan BAL and Suat KIYAK, 2016
 In 2016, Özdikmen, Bal and Kıyak provided new species for Çankırı province,

new records for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 9 below.

Table 9.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

The Genus <i>Labidostomis</i> Germar Of Turkey With A New Species And A New Record (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Clytrinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Labidostomis atkaracalarica</i> sp. nov.	New species (ÇankırıProvince)
	<i>Labidostomis asiatica</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Labidostomis basanica</i> Sahlberg, 1913	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı and Gaziantep provinces and thereby Western half of Anatolia
	<i>Labidostomis beckeri</i> Weise, 1881	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın, Düzce and Zonguldak provinces and thereby Western half of Anatolia
	<i>Labidostomis brevipennis</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı, Hakkari and Konya provinces and thereby Western half of Anatolia
	<i>Labidostomis decipiens</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı and Kayseri provinces
	<i>Labidostomis diversifrons</i> Lefèvre, 1872	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Labidostomis karamanica</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara, Çankırı and Kayseri provinces.
	<i>Labidostomis kaszabi</i> Medvedev, 1962	It has been recorded for the first time from Isparta province.
	<i>Labidostomis longimana</i> (Linnaeus, 1760)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Labidostomis maculipennis</i> Lefèvre, 1870	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Labidostomis medvedevi</i> Warchalowski, 1985	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Isparta province).
	<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Labidostomis mesopotamica</i> Heyden, 1886
<i>Labidostomis oertzeni</i> Weise, 1889		It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province.
<i>Labidostomis pallidipennis</i> (Gebler, 1830)		It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.

	<i>Labidostomis peregrina</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Labidostomis rufa</i> (Waltl, 1838)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Labidostomis sulcicollis</i> (Lacordaire, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.

1.10. Ebru GÜL ASLAN and Medine BAŞAR, 2016

In 2016, Aslan and Başar provided new record for Antalya province and Turkey

with their study. This is included in table 10 below.

Table 10.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Flea beetles collected from olive trees of Antalya Province, including the first record of the monotypic genus <i>Lythrarina</i> Bedel, 1897 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) for Turkey		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Lythrarina salicariae</i> (Paykull, 1800)	<u>It has been recorded for the first time from Turkey (Antalya province)</u>

1.11. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2017

In 2017, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Bal provided new record for Zonguldak province and Turkey with their study. This is included in table 11 below.

Table 11.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

New Food Plants And New Records Of Two Species Of <i>Epitrix</i> Foudras in Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Epitrix hirtipennis</i> (Melsheimer, 1947)	<u>It has been recorded for the first time from Turkey (Zonguldak province)</u>

1.12. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2017

In 2017, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Bal provided new record for various provinces

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 12 below.

Table 12.Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

<i>Phyllotreta</i> Chevrolat in Turkey With A New Record (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Phyllotreta araxicola</i> Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968	<u>It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Çankırı province)</u>
	<i>Phyllotreta astrachanica</i> Lopatin, 1977	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyon, Bartın, Çankırı, Karaman and Zonguldak Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta caucasicola</i> Heikertinger, 1941	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.

	<i>Phyllotreta corrugata</i> Reiche & Saulcy, 1858	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı and Şanlıurfa Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta cruciferae</i> (Goeze, 1777)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın and Zonguldak Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta diademata</i> Foudras, 1860	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta erysimi erysimi</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın, Çankırı and Kayseri Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta fallaciosa</i> Heikertinger, 1941	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara and Kayseri Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta lativittata</i> Kutschera, 1860	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın and Zonguldak Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın and Çankırı Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta nigripes nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyon, Bartın, Bolu and Çankırı provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta nodicornis</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı province.
	<i>Phyllotreta ochripes</i> (Curtis, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time from Zonguldak Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta pontoaegica</i> Gruev, 1982	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta procera</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta punctulata</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara, Bartın and Çankırı Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta striolata</i> (Illiger, 1803)	It has been recorded for the first time from Zonguldak Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta undulata</i> (Kutschera, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara, Bartın, Çankırı, Kayseri and Zonguldak Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta variipennis variipennis</i> (Boieldieu, 1859)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın, Karaman and Zonguldak Provinces.
	<i>Phyllotreta wiseana</i> Jakobson, 1901	It has been recorded for the first time Kayseri Province.

1.13. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, 2017
In 2017, Özdikmen and Coral Şahin provided new species for Ankara province

with their study. This is included in table 13 below.

Table 13. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species, <i>Phyllotreta bilgeae</i> sp. nov., from Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Phyllotreta bilgeae</i> sp. nov.	New species (Ankara Province)

1.14. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2017

In 2017, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin, and Bal provided new species for Ankara, Bartın and Çankırı provinces with their study. This is included in table 14 below.

Table 14. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species Of <i>Phyllotreta</i> Chevrolat from Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Phyllotreta aygulae</i> sp. nov.	New species (Bartın, Ankara, Çankırı Provinces)

1.15. Neslihan BAL, Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN and Suat KIYAK, 2018

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 15 below.

In 2018, Özdikmen, Bal, and Coral Şahin provided new records for Çankırı province

Table 15. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Thirty New Leaf Beetles For The Fauna Of Çankırı Province in Turkey (Chrysomelidae)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina didymata didymata</i> (L. G. Scriba, 1791)	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Chrysolina halysa</i> Bechyně, 1950	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Chrysolina orientalis orientalis</i> (Olivier, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Chrysolina gypsophila</i> (Küster, 1845)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Chrysolina chalcites</i> (Germar, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Chrysolina pseudolurida</i> (Roubal, 1817)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Chrysomela populi</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Entomoscelis adonidis</i> (Pallas, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Entomoscelis suturalis</i> Weise, 1882	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata</i> (Say, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Neophaedon pyritosus</i> (Rossi, 1792)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Plagioderma versicolora</i> (Laicharting, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Prasocuris junci</i> (Brahm, 1790)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Clytra atraphaxidis atraphaxidis</i> (Pallas, 1773)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Clytra novempunctata</i> Olivier, 1808	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Clytra valeriana valeriana</i> Ménétrés, 1832	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Clytra bodemeyeri</i> Weise, 1900	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Black Sea region of Turkey.

	<i>Coptocephala destinoi</i> Fairmaire, 1884	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Coptocephala gelberi</i> Gebler, 1841	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
Criocerinae Latreille, 1804	<i>Crioceris duodecimpunctata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Oulema melanopus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
Donaciinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Donacia bicolora</i> Zschach, 1788	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Calomicrus apicalis</i> Demaison, 1891	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Exosoma flavipes</i> (Heyden, 1878)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Exosoma neglectum</i> Mohr, 1968	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Galeruca armeniaca</i> Weise, 1886	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Galeruca spectabilis orientalis</i> (Osculati, 1844)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Galeruca tanacetii tanacetii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Galerucella calmariensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	It has been new record for Çankırı province and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Xanthogaleruca luteola</i> (O. F. Müller, 1766)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.

1.16. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Neslihan BAL and Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, 2018

In 2018, Özdikmen, Bal, and Coral Şahin provided new records for Çankırı province

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 16 below.

Table 16. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

New Flea Beetles Records Of <i>Aphthona</i> Chevrolat in Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Aphthona atrocaerulea</i> (Stephens, 1831)	It has been the new records for Çankırı and Kayseri provinces and hereby Western Black Sea Region and Central Anatolian Region of Turkey, and the second record for fauna of Turkey.
	<i>Aphthona kuntzei</i> Roubal, 1931	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province
	<i>Aphthona nigriceps</i> Redtenbacher, 1842	It has been the new records for Çankırı and Kayseri provinces and hereby Western Black Sea Region
	<i>Aphthona nigriscutis</i> Foudras, 1860	It has been the new records for Çankırı province and hereby Western Black Sea Region

	<i>Aphthona pallida</i> (Bach, 1859)	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Çankırı province)
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1.17. Neslihan BAL, Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Suat KIYAK, 2018

In 2018, Bal, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Kıyak provided new records for Çankırı and Kayseri provinces with their study. These are included in table 17 below.

Table 17. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Rare Flea Beetles Records For The Fauna Of Turkey From Çankırı Province (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Aeschrocnemis serbica</i> (Kutschera, 1860)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the fourth province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Crepidodera lamina</i> (Bedel, 1901)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the fourth province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Dibolia depressiuscula</i> Letzner, 1847	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the sixth province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Chaetocnema arida</i> Foudras, 1860	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea and Central Anatolian regions of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus australis</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1874)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus hermonensis</i> Furth, 1979	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the fifth province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus kopdagiensis</i> Gruev & Aslan, 1998	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea and Central Anatolian regions of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus reichei</i> (Allard, 1860)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea and Central Anatolian regions of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus scutellaris</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1874)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the fourth province from Turkey and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey
	<i>Longitarsus aubozaorum</i> Biondi, 1997	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Black Sea region of Turkey.

		<u>Moreover, they are the second record for Turkey in after 21 years.</u>
	<i>M. chrysanthemi chrysanthemi</i> (Koch, 1803)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province and hereby Western Black Sea region of Turkey. <u>Moreover, this is the second record for Turkey in after 43 years.</u>
	<i>Psylliodes marcida</i> (Illiger, 1807)	It has been the new records for Çankırı province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Sphaeroderma testaceum</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been the new record for Çankırı province as the fourth province from Turkey.

1.18.Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, Neslihan BAL and Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, 2018
In 2018, Coral Şahin, Bal, and Özdikmen provided new records for Kayseri province

with their study. These are included in table 18 below.

Table 18. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Rare Flea Beetles Records For The Fauna of Turkey From Ankara And Kayseri Provinces (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Dibolia timida</i> Illiger, 1807	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Hermaeophaga ruficollis</i> (Lucas, 1849)	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the fifth province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Longitarsus truncatellus</i> Weise, 1890	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the third province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey
	<i>Psylliodes isatidis</i> Heikertinger, 1913	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the fifth province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Psylliodes saulcyi</i> Allard, 1867	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the second province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey. <u>Moreover, they are the second records for Turkey in after 19 years.</u>
	<i>Psylliodes vindobonnensis</i> Heikertinger, 1914	It has been the new records for Kayseri province as the second province from Turkey and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey. <u>Moreover, they are the second records for Turkey in after 47 years.</u>

1.19. Neslihan BAL, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, 2018
In 2018, Bal, Coral Şahin and Özdikmen provided new records for various provinces

with their study. These are included in table 19 below.

Table 19. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Leaf-Mining And Tortoise Beetles Of Çankırı And Kayseri Provinces in Turkey With New Records (Chrysomelidae: Hispinae And Cassidinae)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Hispinae Gyllenhal, 1813</i>	<i>Hispa atra</i> Linnaeus, 1767	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
<i>Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813</i>	<i>Cassida atrata</i> Fabricius, 1787	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri Province.
	<i>Cassida brevis</i> Weise, 1884	It is the new records for Kayseri province and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey
	<i>Cassida murraea murraea</i> Linnaeus, 1767	It has been the new records for Çankırı province and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey
	<i>Cassida nobilis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Cassida pannonica</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Cassida parvula</i> Boheman, 1854	It has been the new record for Kayseri province, and the second record for Turkey in after 7 years.
<i>Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813</i>	<i>Cassida sanguinolenta</i> O. F. Müller, 1776	It has been the new records for Çankırı province and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey
	<i>Cassida sanguinosa</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been the new record for Çankırı and Kayseri provinces and hereby Central Anatolian region of Turkey. Also they are the second records for Turkey in after 7 years.
	<i>Cassida stigmatica</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Cassida subreticulata</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province.
	<i>Cassida vibex</i> Linnaeus, 1767	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı and Kayseri Province.
	<i>Ischyronota jordanensis</i> Borowiec, 1986	It has been recorded for the first time from Çankırı Province. This is the second record for Turkey in after 24 years.

1.20. Ebru GÜL ASLAN, 2018

In 2018, Aslan provided new records for Konya province with their study. These are included in table 20 below.

Table 20. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Alticini (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) species occurring on Akşehir extensions (Konya) of the Sultan Mountains, Turkey		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae Spinola, 1844</i>	<i>Aphthona franzi</i> Heikertinger, 1944	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.

<i>Aphthona nigriceps</i> Redtenbacher, 1842	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Aphthona warchalowskii</i> Fritschar, 2001	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Chaetocnema conducta</i> (Motschulsky, 1838)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Longitarsus luridus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Longitarsus nigrofasciatus</i> (Goeze, 1777)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Longitarsus pellucidus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Longitarsus picicollis</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Longitarsus succineus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Phyllotreta atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Phyllotreta vittula</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Psylliodes anatolica</i> Gök and Cilbiroglu, 2004	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.
<i>Psylliodes isatidis</i> Heikertinger, 1912	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya Province.

1.21. Ali GÖK and Ergin TURANTEPE, 2019

In 2019, Gök and Turantepe provided new records for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 21 below.

Table 21. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Additions to the fauna of Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera) from Hatila Valley National Park (Artvin, Turkey), with notes on host plant preferences and zoogeographic evaluations		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Altica quercetorum</i> Foudras, 1860	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Aphthona rugipennis</i> Ogluoglu, 1926	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Batophila rubi</i> (Paykull, 1799)	Locality data in Turkey are reported for the first time in this study.
	<i>Chaetocnema scheffleri</i> (Kutschera, 1864)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Crepidodera aurea</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Epitrix pubescens</i> (Koch, 1803)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Longitarsus anchlussae</i> (Paykull 1799)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Longitarsus aramaicus</i> Leonardi, 1979	It has been recorded for the first time in northern Turkey (Artvin Province).
	<i>Longitarsus nasturtii</i> Fabricius, 1792	It has been recorded for the first time in northern Turkey (Artvin Province).
	<i>Neocrepidodera ferruginea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta cruciferae</i> (Goeze, 1777)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Phyllotreta undulata</i> (Kutschera, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.

	<i>Psylliodes napi</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cassida inquinata</i> Brullé, 1832	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Cassida prasina</i> Illiger, 1798	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Cassida rubiginosa</i> Müller, 1776	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Cassida vibex</i> Linnaeus, 1767	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Cassida viridis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
	<i>Hypocassida cornea</i> (Marseul, 1868)	Locality data in Turkey are reported for the first time in this study.
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Phratora coeruleascens</i> Küster, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
Clythrinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Smaragdina vaulogeri</i> (Pic, 1894)	It has been recorded for the first time in northern Turkey (Artvin Province).
Criocerinae Latreille, 1804	<i>Oulema obscura</i> (Stephens, 1831)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus elegantulus</i> Gravenhorst, 1807	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
	<i>Cryptocephalus sexpunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
Eumolpinae Hope, 1840	<i>Bromius obscurus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Galeruca circassica</i> Reitter, 1899	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
	<i>Lochmaea caprea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Xanthogaleruca luteola</i> (Müller, 1766)	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province
	<i>Phyllobrotica elegans</i> Kraatz, 1866	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin Province

1.22. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Tülin KILIÇ, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2019

In 2019, Özdikmen, Kılıç, Coral Şahin and Bal provided new species for İzmir province with their study. This is included in table 22 below.

Table 22. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species Of Flea Beetle Genus <i>Argopus</i> Fisher Von Waldheim, 1824 From Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Argopus circumaeaeagus</i> sp. nov.	New species (İzmir Province)

1.23. Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, 2019

In 2019, Coral Şahin and Özdikmen provided new species for Kayseri

province with their study. This is included in table 23 below.

Table 23. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species of <i>Hydrothassa</i> C. G. Thomson, 1859 from Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Hydrothassa (Agrostithassa) anatolica</i> sp. nov.	New species (Kayseri Province)

1.24. Ali NAFİZ EKİZ, Elisabeth GEİSER, Ali GÖK and Özgür DURMUŞ KAYA, 2020

In 2020, Ekiz, Geiser, Gök and Kaya provided new records for various provinces and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 24 below.

Table 24. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Donaciinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) of Turkey: Species List and New Records		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Donaciinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Donacia aequidorsis</i> Jacobson, 1894	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey
	<i>Donacia aquatica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Kars Provinces.
	<i>Donacia bicolor</i> Zschach, 1788	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Karabük and Mersin Provinces.
	<i>Donacia cinerea</i> Herbst, 1784	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar Province.
	<i>Donacia clavipes</i> Fabricius, 1792	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Bursa, Konya and Erzurum Provinces.
	<i>Donacia crassipes</i> Fabricius, 1775	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu Province.
	<i>Donacia kraatzii</i> Weise, 1881	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Bitlis, Erzurum, and Trabzon Provinces.
	<i>Donacia marginata</i> Hoppe, 1795	It has been recorded for the first time from European part of Istanbul, Afyonkarahisar and Sakarya Provinces.
	<i>Donacia polita</i> Kunze, 1818	It is firstly recorded for Turkey (Adana, Elazığ, and Edirne provinces)
	<i>Donacia simplex</i> Fabricius, 1775	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Mersin, Sakarya and Erzurum Provinces.
	<i>Donacia thalassina</i> Germar, 1811	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Erzurum and Kahramanmaraş Provinces.
	<i>Donacia tomentosa</i> Ahrens, 1810	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Erzurum, Hakkari, Kahramanmaraş and Şanlıurfa Provinces.
	<i>Donacia vulgaris</i> Zschach, 1775	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri Province.
	<i>Plateumaris rustica</i> (Kunze, 1818)	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Bolu province)
<i>Plateumaris sericea</i> (Linnaeus, 1760)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bitlis, Eskişehir, Kastamonu and Sakarya Provinces.	

1.25. Ebru GÜL ASLAN, Özgür DURMUŞ KAYA, Ebru ÜNAL, 2020

In 2020, Aslan, Kaya and Ünal provided new records for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 25 below.

Table 25. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Contributions to the Knowledge of Leaf Beetle (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) Fauna in Elazığ, Erzincan and Tunceli Provinces, Turkey		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica ancyrensis</i> (Weise, 1897)	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
	<i>Altica lythri</i> Aubé, 1843	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan and Tunceli province.
	<i>Longitarsus aeneicollis</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Longitarsus luridus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Longitarsus nanus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Longitarsus nigrofasciatus</i> (Goeze, 1777)	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
	<i>Neocrepidodera ferruginea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
	<i>Psylliodes inflata</i> Reiche and Saulcy, 1858	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Psylliodes tricolor</i> Weise, 1888	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Hypocassida subferruginea</i> (Schrank, 1776)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina hyperici</i> (Forster, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Chrysolina herbacea</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Entomoscelis adonidis</i> (Pallas, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
Clythrinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Clytra weisei</i> Monros, 1953	The present study adds Tunceli for the first time to the distribution area of this species.
	<i>Coptocephala unifasciata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Labidostomis brevipennis</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ and Erzincan provinces.
	<i>Labidostomis cyanicornis</i> (Germar, 1822)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.

	<i>Labidostomis lucida</i> (Germar, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Labidostomis maculipennis</i> Lefèvre, 1870	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Labidostomis mesopotamica</i> Heyden, 1886	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Smaragdina scutellaris</i> (Lefèvre, 1872)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Smaragdina vaulogeri</i> (Pic, 1895)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Tituboea macropus</i> (Illiger, 1800)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
Criocerinae Latreille, 1804	<i>Orsodacne variabilis</i> Bally, 1877	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Lilioceris merdigera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus elegantulus</i> Gravenhorst, 1807	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Cryptocephalus anticus</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
	<i>Cryptocephalus sericeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Pachybrachis excisus</i> (Weise, 1897)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Pachybrachis tessellatus</i> (Olivier, 1791)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Agelastica alni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Calomicrus lividus</i> (Joannis, 1866)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.
	<i>Exosoma thoracicum</i> (Redtenbacher, 1843)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Galeruca armeniaca</i> Weise, 1866	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
	<i>Galeruca jucunda</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Galeruca spectabilis spectabilis</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	The first certain locality record of the subspecies from Erzincan, and confirms its occurrence in Turkey.
	<i>Galerucaspectabilis orientalis</i> Osculati, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ and Erzincan provinces.
	<i>Lochmaea crataegi</i> (Forster, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province.

	<i>Luperus xanthopoda</i> (Schrank, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from Erzincan province.
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1.26. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2020

In 2020, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Bal provided new species for Kayseri

province with their study. This is included in table 26 below.

Table 26. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species Of <i>Cassida</i> Linnaeus, 1758, From Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Cassidinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Cassidinae</i> Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cassida alidagiense</i> sp. nov.	New species (Kayseri Province)

1.27. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Didem CORAL ŞAHİN and Neslihan BAL, 2020

In 2020, Özdikmen, Coral Şahin and Bal provided new subspecies for

Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, and Kayseri provinces with their study. These are included in table 27 below.

Table 27. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Subspecies Of <i>Chrysolina Sanguineocincta</i> (Crotch, 1871) From Turkey (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina</i> (<i>Chalcoidea</i>) <i>sanguineocincta</i> <i>pinarbasiense</i> subsp. nov.	New subspecies (Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, Kayseri Provinces)

1.28. Hüseyin Özdikmen, Neslihan BAL and Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, 2020

In 2020, Özdikmen, Bal and Coral Şahin provided new records for various provinces

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 28 below.

Table 28. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A Contribution To The Knowledge Of Leaf-Beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) in Turkey Using Data Of Specimens In Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum (Turkey, Ankara)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica oleracea oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Bolu, Düzce and Erzincan provinces and hereby from Aegean region of Turkey.
	<i>Aphthona venustula</i> (Kutschera, 1861)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu province and hereby from Black Sea region of Turkey.
	<i>Chaetocnema arenacea</i> (Allard, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province
	<i>Chaetocnema montenegrina</i> Heikertinger, 1912	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province.
	<i>Chaetocnema chlorophana</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time from Amasya province and hereby from Black Sea region of Turkey.

<i>Chaetocnema concinna</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Balıkesir province.
<i>Chaetocnema scheffleri</i> (Kutschera, 1864)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar province.
<i>Crepidodera aurata</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın , Burdur and Tokat provinces.
<i>Epitrix pubescens</i> (Koch, 1803)	It has been recorded for the first time from Samsun province.
<i>Longitarsus callidus</i> Warchałowski, 1967	It has been recorded for the first time from Samsun province and hereby from Black Sea region of Turkey . Also, it is the second record for Turkey .
<i>Longitarsus helvolus</i> Kutschera, 1863	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara , Konya , Nevşehir and Şanlıurfa provinces and hereby from Central Anatolian and South-Eastern Anatolian regions of Turkey . These records are the third report from Turkey .
<i>Longitarsus hermonensis</i> Furth, 1979	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar , Ankara , Çankırı and Konya provinces and hereby for Aegean and Central Anatolian regions of Turkey .
<i>Longitarsus anchusae</i> (Paykull, 1799)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara , Burdur , Çankırı and Kocaeli provinces and hereby from Central Anatolian region of Turkey .
<i>Ochrosis ventralis</i> (Illiger, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Sinop and Şanlıurfa provinces and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey .
<i>Phyllotreta erysimi erysimi</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu province
<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Yozgat province.
<i>Phyllotreta nigripes nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Düzce and Kilis provinces and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey .
<i>Phyllotreta procera</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar and Yozgat provinces and hereby from Aegean region of Turkey .
<i>Podagrica malvae malvae</i> (Illiger, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana province.
<i>Podagrica malvae semirufa</i> (Küster, 1847)	It has been recorded for the first time from İzmir and Manisa provinces and hereby for Turkey.
<i>Psylliodes anatolica</i> Gök & Çilbıroğlu, 2004	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar province and hereby from Aegean region of Turkey . Also, it is the third record for Turkey .
<i>Psylliodes chrysocephala chrysocephala</i> (L., 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Trabzon province.

	<i>Psylliodes pallidicolor</i> Pic, 1903	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara province and hereby from Central Anatolian region of Turkey.	
	<i>Psylliodes tricolor</i> Weise, 1888	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Çankırı and Kilis provinces and hereby for Aegean and South-Eastern Anatolian regions of Turkey.	
Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cassida vittata</i> Villers, 1789	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya province.	
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina americana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Çanakkale province and hereby from Marmara region of Turkey.	
	<i>Chrysolina didymata didymata</i> (Scriba, 1791)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province	
	<i>Chrysolina coeruleans angelica</i> (Reiche & Saulcy, 1858)	It has been recorded for the first time Adana and Diyarbakır provinces and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.	
	<i>Chrysolina herbacea herbacea</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time Afyonkarahisar, Amasya and Gümüşhane provinces.	
	<i>Chrysolina anceyi anceyi</i> (Marseul, 1868)	It has been recorded for the first time Şanlıurfa province and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey. Also, it is the second record for Turkey	
	<i>Chrysomela populi</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time Mersin province	
	<i>Chrysomela saliceti saliceti</i> (Weise, 1884)	It has been recorded for the first time Bitlis and Burdur provinces.	
	<i>Entomoscelis adonidis</i> (Pallas, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time Burdur and Karaman provinces	
	<i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata</i> (Say, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time Kırıkkale province.	
	<i>Plagiodera versicolora</i> (Laicharting, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from Balıkesir province.	
	Clythrinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Clytra laeviuscula</i> Ratzeburg, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time Adana province.
		<i>Clytra novempunctata</i> Olivier, 1808	It has been recorded for the first time Afyonkarahisar and Sakarya provinces
		<i>Coptocephala destinoi</i> Fairmaire, 1884	It has been recorded for the first time Şanlıurfa province and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
<i>Coptocephala gelberi</i> (Gebler, 1841)		It has been recorded for the first time Afyonkarahisar, Aydın, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Eskişehir, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kocaeli and Şanlıurfa provinces and hereby from Aegean and South-Eastern Anatolian regions of Turkey.	
<i>Labidostomis kaszabi</i> (Medvedev, 1962)		It has been recorded for the first time Afyonkarahisar province and hereby from Aegean region of Turkey.	

	<i>Labidostomis metallica metallica</i> Lefèvre, 1872	It has been s recorded for the first time Çankırı province and hereby from Central Anatolian region of Turkey . Also, it is the second record for Turkey .
	<i>Lachnaia sexpunctata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time İzmir province.
	<i>Smaragdina biornata angorensis</i> (Lopatin, 2002)	It has been recorded for the first time Çankırı , Konya and Niğde provinces. Also, these are the second provincial records for Turkey after Ankara province .
	<i>Smaragdina concolor concolor</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Osmanive province)
	<i>Smaragdina flavicollis</i> (Charpentier, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time Ankara province.
	<i>Smaragdina hypocrita</i> (Lacordaire, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time Afyonkarahisar province.
	<i>Smaragdina vaulogeri</i> (Pic, 1895)	It has been recorded for the first time Düzce province and hereby from Black Sea region of Turkey in Northern Anatolia.
	<i>Tituboea macropus</i> (Illiger, 1800)	It has been recorded for the first time Diyarbakır province and hereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey .
Criocerinae Latreille, 1804	<i>Oulema melanopus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time Çankırı and Tokat provinces.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus fulvus fulvus</i> Goeze, 1777	It has been recorded for the first time Van province
	<i>Cryptocephalus pygmaeus vittula</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time Ankara province.
	<i>Cryptocephalus bipunctatus bipunctatus</i> (L., 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time Giresun province.
	<i>Cryptocephalus duplicatus</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been recorded for the first time Bartın province.
	<i>Cryptocephalus flavipes</i> Fabricius, 1781	It has been recorded for the first time Zonguldak province.
	<i>Pachybrachis fimbriolatus</i> (Suffrian, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time Sakarya province.
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Aulacophora foveicollis</i> (Lucas, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time Ankara and Antalya provinces.
	<i>Diorhabda carinata</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time Kayseri province and hereby from Central Anatolian region of Turkey .
	<i>Diorhabda elongata</i> (Brullé, 1832)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province.
	<i>Exosoma thoracicum</i> (Redtenbacher, 1843)	It has been recorded for the first time from Burdur province
	<i>Galeruca interrupta</i> (Illiger, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar , Burdur , Kırşehir and Nevşehir provinces and hereby from Aegean region of Turkey .
	<i>Galeruca spectabilis orientalis</i> (Osculati, 1844)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu province
	<i>Nymphius lydius</i> (Weise, 1886)	It has been recorded for the first time Tokat province.
	<i>Radymna persica</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time Isparta province and hereby from

		Mediterranean region of Turkey.
	<i>Xanthogaleruca luteola</i> (Müller, 1766)	It has been recorded for the first time from Edirne, Hatay, Kars and Konya provinces.

1.29. Ali Gök and Kadir BOSTAN, 2020
In 2020, Özdikmen, Bal and Coral Şahin provided new records for 26 Ağustos Nature

Park (Afyonkarahisar province) with their study. These are included in table 29 below.

Table 29. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

The First Faunistic Data on the Leaf Beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) of 26 Ağustos Nature Park, Afyonkarahisar, Turkey		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica carduorum</i> Guérin-Méneville, 1858	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Altica oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Aphthona pygmaea</i> (Kutschera, 1861)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Chaetocnema concinna</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Chaetocnema coyeyi</i> (Allard, 1864)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Chaetocnema mannerheimi</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Chaetocnema obesa</i> (Boieldieu, 1859)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Crepidodera aurata</i> (Marsham, 1802)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Longitarsus bertii</i> Leonardi, 1973	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Longitarsus fallax</i> Weise, 1888	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Longitarsus fuscoaeus</i> Redtenbacher, 1849	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Longitarsus kutscherae</i> (Rye, 1872)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Longitarsus longipennis</i> Kutschera, 1863	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
<i>Longitarsus lycopi</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It is recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)	

	<i>Longitarsus pellucidus</i> (Foudras, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Neocrepidodera ferruginea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta corrugata</i> Reiche & Saulcy, 1858	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta ochripes</i> (Curtis, 1837)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta procera</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Phyllotreta vittula</i> (Redtenbacher, 1849)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Psylliodes circumdata</i> (Redtenbacher, 1842)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Psylliodes napi</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Psylliodes tricolor</i> Weise, 1888	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cassida nobilis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Cassida pannonica</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Cassida rubiginosa</i> Müller, 1776	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Cassida seraphina</i> Ménétriés, 1836	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Hypocassida cornea</i> (Marseul, 1868)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysomela populi</i> Linnaeus, 1758	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Colaphellus sophiae</i> (Schaller, 1783)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Entomoscelis adonidis</i> (Pallas, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Gastrophysa polygoni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata</i> (Say, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)

	<i>Plagioder a versicolora</i> (Laicharting, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Clythrinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Labidostomis cyanicornis</i> (Germar, 1822)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Labidostomis oertzeni</i> Weise, 1889	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Criocerinae Latreille, 1804	<i>Oulema rufocyanea</i> (Suffrian, 1847)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus connexus</i> Olivier, 1807	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Cryptocephalus duplicatus</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Cryptocephalus moraei</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Pachybrachis fimbriolatus</i> (Suffrian, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Eumolpinae Hope, 1840	<i>Pachnephorus villosus</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Galeruca interrupta</i> Illiger, 1802	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)
	<i>Luperus xanthopoda</i> (Schrank, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from 26 Ağustos Nature Park (Afyonkarahisar)

1.30. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Esat PEHLİVAN, Neslihan BAL, Yusuf KARSAVURAN and Serdar TEZCAN, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen, Pehlivan, Bal, Karsavuran and Tezcan provided new record for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 30 below.

Table 30. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A Contribution To The Fauna Of Turkish Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera: Chrysomeloidea)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Alticinae Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica hampei</i> Allard, 1867	It has been recorded for the first time from Hatay province, and therefore from Mediterranean region .
	<i>Podagrica malvae malvae</i> (Illiger, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kütahya province.
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina polita polita</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bahkesir province.
	<i>Chrysolina didymata didymata</i> (Scriba, 1791)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kütahya, Muğla and Samsun provinces.
	<i>Chrysolina didymata syriaca</i> (Weise, 1884)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, Diyarbakır, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Siirt and Şanlıurfa provinces.

<i>Chrysolina hyperici hyperici</i> (Forster, 1771)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bilecik, Kars, Muğla and Rize provinces.
<i>Chrysolina orientalis</i> (Olivier, 1807)	It has been recorded for the first time from Antalya, Burdur, Çorum, Denizli, Gaziantep, Hakkari, Karaman, Malatya, Mardin, Muğla and Uşak provinces in Asian Turkey (Anatolia), and Kırklareli province in European Turkey (Thrace).
<i>Chrysolina vernalis otomana</i> (Weise, 1906)	It has been recorded for the first time from Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bolu, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Manisa, Muğla, Sakarya and Van provinces in Asian Turkey and Edirne, Kırklareli provinces in European Turkey.
<i>Chrysolina gypsophilae</i> (Küster, 1845)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, Denizli, Diyarbakır and Kayseri provinces, and therefore from South-Eastern Anatolian region .
<i>Chrysolina chalcites</i> (Germar, 1824)	It has been recorded for the first time from Balıkesir, Bilecik, Çanakkale and Kayseri provinces.
<i>Chrysolina coerulans angelica</i> (Reiche & Saulcy, 1858)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Aydın, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Malatya, Manisa, Şanlıurfa and Siirt provinces, and therefore for Eastern Anatolian region and South-Eastern Anatolian region .
<i>Chrysolina herbacea alacris</i> Bechyné, 1950	It has been recorded for the first time from Aydın, Denizli, İzmir, Malatya, Muğla provinces, and therefore from Aegean region and Eastern Anatolian region .
<i>Chrysolina reitteri</i> (Weise, 1884)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ağrı, Çorum, Karaman, Kars and Kütahya provinces, and therefore from Aegean region .
<i>Chrysolina pseudolurida</i> (Roubal, 1817)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kütahya province, and therefore from Aegean region .
<i>Colaphellus sophiae transsylvanicus</i> Machatschke, 1954	It has been recorded for the first time from Gümüşhane province.
<i>Neophaedon pyritosus</i> (Rossi, 1792)	It has been recorded for the first time from Aydın, Balıkesir, Bolu, Bursa, Kütahya, Mersin and Zonguldak provinces.
<i>Phratora vitellinae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Gümüşhane province.

	<i>Plagiodera versicolora</i> (Laicharting, 1781)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana and Bartın provinces.
Clythrinae Kirby, 1837	<i>Smaragdina tibialis</i> (Brullé, 1832)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın, Karaman, Mersin, Sinop, Sivas and Zonguldak provinces.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus fulvus</i> Goeze, 1777	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Artvin, Çorum, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Kahramanmaraş, Nevşehir, Samsun, Siirt, Şanlıurfa and Van provinces, and therefore from South-Eastern Anatolian region .
	<i>Cryptocephalus ocellatus ocellatus</i> Drapiez, 1819	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Bitlis, Düzce, Kahramanmaraş, Siirt and Uşak provinces.
	<i>Cryptocephalus anticus</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Çorum and Şanlıurfa provinces.
	<i>Cryptocephalus flavipes</i> Fabricius, 1781	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın and Zonguldak provinces.
	<i>Cryptocephalus janthinus</i> Germar, 1824	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu province, and therefore from Black Sea region .
	<i>Cryptocephalus moraei</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bartın and Karaman provinces.
	<i>Cryptocephalus sericeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Van province.
	<i>Pachybrachis excisus</i> (Weise, 1897)	It has been recorded for the first time from Afyonkarahisar, Bitlis, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Kahramanmaraş, Kırşehir, Kütahya and Mardin provinces, and therefore from Aegean region, South-Eastern Anatolian region .
	<i>Pachybrachis glycyrrhizae</i> (Olivier, 1808)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, Batman, Diyarbakır, Hatay, Siirt and Şırnak provinces.
	<i>Pachybrachis mardinensis</i> (Weise, 1900)	It has been recorded for the first time from Konya, Uşak provinces in Asian Turkey (Anatolia), and therefore from Central Anatolian region .
	<i>Pachybrachis tessellatus tauricus</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, Bartın, Bilecik, Çanakkale, Eskişehir, Giresun, Hatay, Kastamonu, Malatya, Muğla, Muş, Ordu, Samsun and Uşak provinces.
	Eumolpinae Hope, 1840	<i>Pachnephorus villosus</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)

		therefore for South-Eastern Anatolian region .
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1.31. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Neslihan BAL and Halil BOLU, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen, Bal and Bolu provided new species for Elazığ province with their study. This is included in table 31 below.

Table 31. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New Species of <i>Aphthona</i> Chevrolat From Turkey (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Aphthona harputensis</i> sp. nov.	New species (Elazığ Province)

1.32. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Halil BOLU and Neslihan BAL, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen, Bolu and Bal provided new record for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 32 below.

Table 32. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A Contribution To The Knowledge Of Cerambycidae And Chrysomelidae in Turkey (Coleoptera: Cerambycoidea And Chrysomeloidea)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Alticinae</i> Spinola, 1844	<i>Altica lythri</i> Aubé, 1843	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Altica palustris</i> (Weise, 1888)	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
<i>Cassidinae</i> Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cassida brevis</i> Weise, 1884	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province
	<i>Cassida denticollis</i> Suffrian, 1844	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province and thereby from Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey. Moreover, it is the second record for Turkey.
	<i>Cassida margaritacea</i> Schaller, 1783	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ and Mardin provinces and thereby from Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina herbacea alacris</i> Bechyné, 1950	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Clytra atraphaxidis atraphaxidis</i> (Pallas, 1773)	It has been recorded for the first time from Şanlıurfa province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
	<i>Smaragdina chloris chloris</i> (Lacordaire, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey. Moreover, it is the second record for Turkey.
	<i>Smaragdina hypocrita</i> (Lacordaire, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province

	<i>Smaragdina limbata</i> (Steven, 1806)	It has been recorded for the first time from Şanlıurfa province
	<i>Smaragdina scutellaris</i> (Lefèvre, 1872)	It has been recorded for the first time from Elazığ province and thereby from Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey. Moreover, it is recorded for the third time from Turkey.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus fulvus schatzmayri</i> Burlini, 1969	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.
Galerucinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Galeruca spectabilis orientalis</i> (Osculati, 1844)	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province and thereby from South-Eastern Anatolian region of Turkey.

1.33. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Yusuf KARSAVURAN, Neslihan BAL, Serdar TEZCAN and Esat PEHLİVAN, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen, Karsavuran, Bal, Tezcan and Pehlivan provided new record for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 33 below.

Table 33. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

New Data On Rare And A Little-Known Leaf Beetle (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) Species From Turkey Along With New Locality Records		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Chrysolina sanguineocincta pınarbasiense</i> Özdikmen, Coral Şahin & Bal, 2020	It has been recorded for the first time from Balıkesir, Bursa, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Karaman and Kars provinces in Asian Turkey, and therefore from Eastern Anatolian region, Marmara region.
	<i>Chrysolina cerealis cerealis</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ankara, Elazığ, İzmir and Mardin provinces, and therefore from Aegean region, Central Anatolian region, Eastern Anatolian region and South-Eastern Anatolian region.
	<i>Chrysolina haemoptera haemoptera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bolu, Elazığ, Kastamonu, Sakarya provinces, and therefore from Black Sea region, Eastern Anatolian region and Asian part of Marmara region. In addition, it is also the first record for Asian Turkey (Anatolia) objectively with real locality data.
	<i>Chrysolina adzharica excavata</i> Kippenberg, 2012	It has been the first report after 9 years from the original description of the subspecies.
	<i>Gastrophysa viridula viridula</i> (DeGeer, 1775)	It has been recorded for the first time from Gümüşhane province
	<i>Hydrothassa anatolica</i> Coral Şahin & Özdikmen, 2019	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, İzmir, Malatya and Yalova provinces in Asian Turkey, and therefore from Aegean region, Eastern Anatolian region, Anatolian part of

		Marmara region and South-Eastern Anatolian region.
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus phaleratus</i> (Tappes, 1871)	It has been recorded for the first time from Tunceli province and therefore from Eastern Anatolian region .
	<i>Cryptocephalus tappesi</i> Marseul, 1868	It has been recorded for the first time from Şırnak province
	<i>Cryptocephalus elegantulus</i> Gravenhorst, 1807	It has been recorded for the first time from Bitlis and Van provinces.
	<i>Cryptocephalus quinquepunctatus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	It has been recorded for the first time from Antalya province, and therefore from Mediterranean region and also Turkey.
	<i>Cryptocephalus surdus</i> Rapilly, 1980	It has been recorded for the first time from Diyarbakır province, and therefore from South-Eastern Anatolian region . In addition, it is the second record for Turkey .
	<i>Pachybrachis nigropunctatus</i> (Suffrian, 1854)	It has been recorded for the first time from Mardin and Şanlıurfa provinces, and therefore from SouthEastern Anatolian region .
	<i>Pachybrachis pentheri</i> (Ganglbauer, 1905)	It has been recorded for the first time from Ağrı, Artvin, Hakkari, Iğdır, Kahramanmaraş, Manisa and Zonguldak provinces, and therefore from Aegean region, Black Sea region, Eastern Anatolian region .
	<i>Pachybrachis scripticollis</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman province
	<i>Stylosomus flavus flavus</i> Marseul, 1875	It has been recorded for the first time from Artvin, Denizli, İzmir and Malatya provinces in Asian Turkey (Anatolia), and therefore from Aegean region and Eastern Black Sea region .

1.34. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN, Serdar TEZCAN, Neslihan BAL, Yusuf KARSAVURAN and Esat PEHLİVAN, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen, Tezcan, Bal, Karsavuran and Pehlivan provided new record for various provinces with their study. These are included in table 34 below.

Table 34. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study
New Leaf Beetle Records For European Turkey (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae)

FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus chrysopus</i> Gmelin, 1790	It has been recorded for the first time from Tekirdağ province, and therefore for Marmara region and European Turkey objectively with real locality data.
	<i>Cryptocephalus populi</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bingöl, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Erzincan, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kayseri, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Yozgat and

		Zonguldak provinces in Asian Turkey (Anatolia), and therefore from Aegean region, Black Sea region, Eastern Anatolian region . In addition, it is the first record for Tekirdağ province in European Turkey (Thrace), and therefore Marmara region and also for European Turkey (Thrace).
	<i>Cryptocephalus pygmaeus vittula</i> Suffrian, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Edirne and Tekirdağ provinces in European Turkey (Thrace), and therefore from European Turkey objectively with real locality data.
	<i>Cryptocephalus turcicus</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been recorded for the first time from Tekirdağ province in European Turkey (Thrace), and also European Turkey objectively with real locality data.
	<i>Pachybrachis mendax mendax</i> (Suffrian, 1860)	It has been recorded for the first time from Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Antalya, Bingöl, Bolu, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hakkari, Iğdır, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Siirt and Şırnak provinces in Asian Turkey (Anatolia), and therefore for South-Eastern Anatolian region . In addition, it is the first record from Kırklareli and Tekirdağ provinces in European Turkey (Thrace), and therefore for European Turkey .
	<i>Pachybrachis tessellatus tessellatus</i> (Olivier, 1791)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kırklareli and Tekirdağ provinces, and therefore from European Turkey and also Turkey.
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Gonioctena fornicata</i> (Brüggemann, 1873)	It has been recorded for the first time from Bursa and Kırklareli provinces, and therefore from European Turkey objectively with real locality data.

1.35. Hüseyin ÖZDİKMEN and Didem CORAL ŞAHİN, 2021

In 2021, Özdikmen and Coral Şahin provided new record for Kayseri province

and Turkey with their study. These are included in table 35 below.

Table 35. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Leaf Beetles of Kayseri Province With New and Interesting Data For Turkey: Part I - Subfamilies Donaciinae to Galerucinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae)		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802	<i>Colaphellus sophiae amasiae</i> Machatschke, 1954	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Phaedon armoraciae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Phratora laticollis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province. and

		<u>thereby the third report from Turkey.</u>
	<i>Phratora vitellinae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Clytra atraphaxidis atraphaxidis</i> (Pallas, 1773)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Clytra bodemeyeri bodemeyeri</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Labidostomis cyanicornis</i> Germar, 1822	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Labidostomis medvedevi</i> Warchalowski, 1985	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and <u>thereby the second report from Turkey.</u>
	<i>Labidostomis metallica metallica</i> Lefevre, 1872	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and <u>thereby the third report from Turkey.</u>
	<i>Labidostomis peregrina</i> Weise, 1900	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Labidostomis rufa</i> (Waltl, 1838)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Labidostomis sulcicollis</i> Lacordaire, 1848	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Smaragdina affinis affinis</i> (Illiger, 1794)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and <u>thereby to Central Anatolian region.</u> Moreover, <u>it is reported from Turkey for the second time after 46 years from its first record</u>
	<i>Smaragdina biornata angorensis</i> Lopatin, 2002	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province. Moreover, <u>it is reported for the fourth time.</u>
	<i>Smaragdina hypocrita</i> (Lacordaire, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Smaragdina judaica</i> (Lefevre, 1872)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and <u>thereby to Central Anatolian region.</u>
	<i>Smaragdina limbata</i> (Steven, 1806)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province.
<i>Cryptocephalinae</i> Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus elegantulus</i> Gravenhorst, 1807	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus fausti</i> Weise, 1882	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus fulvus fulvus</i> Goeze, 1777	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus cribratus</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus duplicatus</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus sericeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Cryptocephalus wehnckei</i> Weise, 1881	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Pachybrachis fimbriolatus</i> (Suffrian, 1848)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
<i>Donaciinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Donacia kraatzii</i> Weise, 1881	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and <u>thereby to Central Anatolian region.</u>
	<i>Donacia marginata</i> Hoppe, 1795	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province

<i>Eumolpinae</i> Hope, 1840	<i>Pachnophorus villosus</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
<i>Galerucinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Calomicrus apicalis</i> Demaison, 1891	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Galeruca armeniaca</i> Weise, 1886	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Luperus flavipes flavipes</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Luperus floralis</i> Faldermann, 1837	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Luperus xanthopoda</i> Schrank, 1781	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Nymphius forcipifer</i> (Weise, 1900)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Nymphius lydius</i> (Weise, 1886)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province
	<i>Nymphius stylifer stylifer</i> (Weise, 1899)	It has been recorded for the first time from Kayseri province and thereby to Central Anatolian region of Turkey.

2. FOREIGN RESEARCHERS WHO HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO THE CHRYSOMELIDAE FAUNA OF TURKEY SINCE 2014

2.1. Lev NIKANDROVICH MEDVEDEV, 2015

In 2015, Medvedev added 3 new records and one new subspecies to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 36].

Table 36. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

To the knowledge of leaf beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) from Turkey		
FAMILIES	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Chrysomelinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Gonioctena linnaeana</i> (Schrank, 1781)	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Tunceli province)
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Smaragdina djebellina</i> (Lefèvre, 1872)	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Hakkari province)
<i>Cryptocephalinae</i> Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus concolor</i> Suffrian, 1847	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Sinop province)
	<i>Cryptocephalus rugicollis otomana</i> subsp. n.	It has been a New subspecies (Denizli and Manisa province)

2.2. JAN BEZDĚK, 2015

In 2015, Bezděk added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 37].

Table 37. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A Review of Palaearctic <i>Scelolyperus</i> (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae), with description of s. <i>Perreus</i> sp. Nov. from Turkey		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Galerucinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Scelolyperus perreus</i> Bezděk sp. nov.	New species (Adiyaman Province)

2.3. Klaus-Wemer ANTON and Alex DELOBEL, 2017

In 2017, Anton and Delobel added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 38].

Table 38. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

Three new Asian species of <i>Bruchidius</i> (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Bruchinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Bruchidius planicornis</i> sp. nov.	New species (Van Province)

2.4. Jan BEZDĚK and Renato REGALIN, 2017

In 2017, Bezděk and Regalin added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 39].

Table 39. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A review of <i>Labidostomis</i> species similar to <i>L. longimana</i> from southeastern Europe with descriptions of two new species from Greece and Turkey (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Cryptocephalinae: Clytrini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Clytrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Labidostomis (Labidostomis) leonardii</i> sp. nov.	New species (Isparta Province)

2.5. José MIQUEL VELA and Gloria BASTAZO, 2017

In 2017, Vela and Bastazo added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 40].

Table 40. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

<i>Luperus doeberli</i>, New Species from Southeastern Turkey (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Galerucinae</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Luperus doeberli</i> n. sp.	New species (Hakkari Province)

2.6. Franck DUHALDEBORDE, 2018

In 2018, Duhaldeborde added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 41].

Table 41. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

A New <i>Cryptocephalus</i> from Turkey of the <i>C. flavipes</i> Fabricius, 1781, species-group (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Cryptocephalini)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Clythrinae</i> Kirby, 1837	<i>Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cilicius</i> n. sp.	New species (Mersin Province)

2.7. Horst KIPPENBERG, 2019

In 2019, Kippenberg added one new species to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 42].

Table 42. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

<i>Rhodopaea heinzi</i> sp. n. aus Anatolien (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Eumolpinae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Eumolpinae</i> Hope, 1840	<i>Rhodopaea heinzi</i> sp.n.	New species (İzmit Province)

2.8. Matthias SCHÖLLER, 2020

In 2020, Matthias added one new records to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey with this study [Table 43].

Table 43. Contributions to the Chrysomelidae fauna with the study

New country records, taxonomical changes and a new species in Palaearctic Cryptocephalinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae)		
FAMILY	SPECIES/SUBSPECIES	STATUS OF THE SPECIES
<i>Cryptocephalinae</i> Gyllenhal, 1813	<i>Cryptocephalus subruber</i> Rapilly, 1980	It has been firstly recorded for Turkey (Kahramanmaraş province)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Since 2014, 35 articles have been contributed to the Chrysomelidae fauna of Turkey by Turkish researchers and 8 articles have been contributed by foreign researchers. Among foreign researchers, **Jan BEZDEK** was the one who contributed the most to the fauna with a rate of 18%. Of the domestic researchers, the largest contribution to the fauna was made by **Hüseyin ÖZDIKMEN** with 70%.

Turkish researchers have made an important contribution to the fauna of Chrysomelidae by identifying 14 new records, 9 new species and one new subspecies for Turkey through their studies

conducted since 2014 (Fig. 1). Foreign researchers have made significant contributions to the fauna of our country with 4 new records, 6 new species and 1 new subspecies through their studies (Fig. 2). In short, a total of 18 new records, 15 new species, 2 new subspecies have been added to the Chrysomelidae fauna since 2014 to the present day.

The following chart shows the researchers who contributed to the Chrysomelidae fauna of our country in 2014 and after, and the new species, new subspecies and new record numbers they added to the fauna.

Figure 1. Turkish researchers who contributed to the Chrysomelidae fauna of our country in 2014 and later and their contributions

The new species that Turkish researchers have added to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna are as follows:

Chrysolina (Lopatinica) kabalaki sp. n.
Cheilotoma cankiriensis spec. nov.
Labidostomis atkaracalarica sp. nov.
Hydrothassa (Agrostithassa) anatolica sp. nov.

Argopus circumaeadeagus sp. nov.
Cassida alidagiense sp. nov.
Aphthona harputensis sp. nov.
Phyllotreta bilgeae sp. nov.
Phyllotreta aygulae sp. nov.

The new records added by Turkish researchers to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna are as follows:

Longitarsus aeruginosus (Foudras, 1860)
Longitarsus brunneus (Duftschmidt, 1825)
Psylliodes laticollis Kutschera, 1864
Chrysolina (Paradiachalcoidea) dohrnii dohrnii
Pachnephorus corinthius Fairmaire, 1862
Lythraria salicariae (Paykull, 1800)
Podagrica malvae semirufa (Küster, 1847)
Epitrix hirtipennis (Melsheimer, 1947)

Phyllotreta araxicola Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968
Aphthona pallida (Bach, 1859)
Donacia aequidorsis Jacobson, 1894
Donacia polita Kunze, 1818
Plateumaris rustica (Kunze, 1818)
Labidostomis medvedevi Warchalowski, 1985

The new subspecies added to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna by Turkish researchers are as follows:

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) sanguineocincta pinarbasiense subsp. nov.

Figure 2. Foreign researchers who contributed to the Chrysomelidae fauna of our country in 2014 and later and their contributions

The new species that foreign researchers have added to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna are as follows:

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) leonardii sp. nov.

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cilicius n. sp.

Bruchidius planicornis sp. nov.

Rhodopaea heinzi sp. n.

Luperus doeberli n. sp.

Scelolyperus perreus Bezděk sp. nov.

The new records added by foreign researchers to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna are as follows:

Gonioctena linnaeana (Schrank, 1781)

Cryptocephalus subruber Rapilly, 1980

Smaragdina djebellina (Lefèvre, 1872)

Cryptocephalus concolor Suffrian, 1847

The new subspecies added to our country's Chrysomelidae fauna by foreign researchers are as follows:

Cryptocephalus rugicollis ottomana subsp. n.

Foreign researchers have added 6 New species to the fauna of our country Chrysomelidae: *Labidostomis (Labidostomis) leonardii* sp. nov., *Bruchidius planicornis* sp. nov., *Luperus doeberli* n. sp., *Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cilicius* n. sp., *Rhodopaea heinzi* sp.n., *Scelolyperus perreus* Bezděk sp. nov; 4 new records: *Gonioctena*

linnaeana (Schrank, 1781), *Smaragdina djebellina* (Lefèvre, 1872), *Cryptocephalus concolor* Suffrian, 1847, *Cryptocephalus subruber* Rapilly, 1980; 1 new subspecies: *Cryptocephalus rugicollis ottomana* subsp. n. is. As a result, with the contributions of Turkish and foreign researchers, 4 new species belonging to the Alticinae subfamily; 1 new species belonging to

Bruchinae subfamily; 1 new species belonging to Cassidinae subfamily; 3 new species and 1 subspecies belonging to subfamily Chrysomelinae; 3 new species belonging to the subfamily Clytrinae; 2 new species belonging to Galerucinae subfamily and 1 new species belonging to Eumolpinae subfamily have been added to the Turkish Chrysomelidae fauna.

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